

Abstracts Book

Conference on Connecting Health and Climate Change
October 11-12 in Stockholm, Sweden

The hybrid conference is organised as part of the EU-funded project ENBEL - Enhancing Belmont Research Action to support EU policy making on climate change and health. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101003966.

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ISBN: 978-91-8070-316-1

Publisher: Umeå University

First Published Date: 2024-02-14

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Sustainable solutions in climate action - the role of medical doctors

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Keywords: climate change, medical doctors, sustainable solutions

Introduction: This study aims to measure physicians' awareness of climate change impacts on health and their perceptions of their role in climate action (Turkey, Serbia, international group)

Methods: Data were collected online using a questionnaire created by the researchers. Attempts were made to reach physicians in Turkey, Serbia, and Europe through medical professional associations.

Results: More than 500 physicians, 70% from Turkey, answered the questionnaire. More respondents were female, had at least one child, were clinicians, worked in a hospital, and lived in a large city. Most physicians indicated that climate change poses a serious threat to health, and they are concerned about it. They also noted that climate action can mitigate climate change and adapt to the climate by changing our habits, and changes in government policy can accelerate this adaptation. Responses showed that physicians are aware of the health impacts of climate change. Physicians believe that while their colleagues play an important role in addressing the health impacts of climate change, they need more expertise and capacity building, and the health sector is not adequately prepared.

Conclusions: Medical doctors have a privileged position in taking action for sustainable solutions to climate change. Their capacity should be expanded in climate mitigation and adaptation action.